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Lab-scale validation results

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Nomenclature

Acronyms

CAN Controller Area Network

CHIL Controller Hardware-in-the-Loop

HIL Hardware-in-the-Loop

HMI Human-Machine Interface

MPC Model Predictive Control

OPF Optimal Power Flow

PHIL Power Hardware-in-the-Loop

PLL Phase-Locked Loop

RMS Root Mean Square

RT-Lab Real-Time Laboratory software suite by Opal-RT

SCADA Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition

SOP Soft Open Point

VPN Virtual Private Network

Symbols

$\cos \phi$ Power factor

I_{RMS} RMS current [A]

P Active power [W]

Q Reactive power [VAR]

V_{RMS} RMS voltage [V]

1 Executive Summary

This Deliverable illustrates the work carried out on the laboratory and hardware-in-the-loop validation of the operation and control of multiport converters (MPCs) in distribution grids within the context of iPLUG project.

As stated in previous deliverables, MPCs are power electronics devices that allow the interconnection of multiple sources and loads in unidirectional or bidirectional ports of a single device. These sources or loads could be distributed energy resources and grid sections, like feeders or microgrids.

The main objective of WP4 is to demonstrate the capability of integrating MPCs into the distribution grid seamlessly. This integration requires the development of control strategies, which are validated through experimental tests as required in task T4.4.

The tests developed in this deliverable will be focused on local controllers for isolated soft open points and optimal operation of soft open points in distribution grids. As a reminder, the soft open point is a concept that aims to enhance the operation of distribution networks by replacing traditional switches with controllable power electronics devices, enabling features beyond grid reconfiguration by controlling active and reactive power at each port.

This deliverable focuses on HIL tests development through three main stages: Digital real-time simulations, controller HIL, and power HIL. The introduction, in Chapter 2, makes a conceptual review of real-time simulation, hardware-in-the-loop simulation, and the main applications in power systems.

The subsequent chapters follow the next structure.

- Chapter 3 summarizes the development and validation of a digital real-time simulation of an isolated MPC, the triple active bridge converter. The operation and control principles are briefly reviewed, and the switching model is presented. Furthermore, the TAB switching model is implemented and tested in open-loop operation using the Typhoon HIL environment, which validates the capability of running real-time simulations with this model.
- Chapter 4 presents the validation of the control strategy of the TAB and a TAB-based soft open point using the controller HIL approach. In the chapter, the controller HIL concepts and equipment used in the laboratory testbed are presented. Furthermore, the TAB power flow decoupling control strategy is introduced and validated using a commercial microcontroller connected to the Typhoon HIL device. The same approach is used for a TAB-based soft open point. The results of the validation are presented and analyzed.
- Chapter 5, focuses on the validation of a centralized coordination through high-level

optimization. The testbed deployed at IREC’s Energy Laboratory is presented in detail. Then, different stages of the testbed validation are introduced, such as the model development and its adaptation for power HIL tests. Finally, the results of the tests are presented and discussed, validating the strategy and methodology proposed in iPLUG.

2 Introduction

The worldwide effort to reduce greenhouse gas emissions by transitioning from fossil-fuel-based energy resources to renewable energy is accompanied by significant changes in power grids. They are evolving from centralized systems, based on large power plants that rely on synchronous generators, to decentralized networks, whose distributed generation systems employ converter-driven technologies. In a scenario with high penetration of power electronics-interfaced assets into the power grid's operation and dynamics, it is crucial to investigate innovative converter topologies and enhance their control systems. This Deliverable describes hardware-in-the-loop (HIL) testing of multiport converters (MPCs), a converter topology including more than two ports. MPCs have different potential applications in energy systems: for example, they can be employed as energy hubs that coordinate multiple distributed energy sources, eliminating the need for a specific converter connection for each resource and the coordination of their control and operation when they provide services to the grid as an aggregated entity. Another application of MPCs is the enhancement of soft open points (SOPs), which is investigated in this Deliverable.

The concept of SOP is relatively recent, and its initial definition was based on a two-port power electronics device consisting of a back-to-back voltage source converter (VSC) that interconnects two distribution system feeders, unlocking power flow control and improving the operation of hard switches. SOPs, therefore, may enable greater operational flexibility, controllability, and reliability in distribution networks [3]. This could lead to reduced energy losses, reduced renewable energy curtailment, deferred need for infrastructure reinforcement, improved energy arbitrage, and voltage management [4]. Moreover, SOPs' operation and impact can be improved by applying the MPC concept, which concentrates VSC and DC-DC converters in a single piece of hardware managed by a centralized power flow controller.

iPLUG's Deliverable D4.1 [5] described the utilization of MPCs in SOPs, detailing their modelling, primary control, and optimal power dispatch in distribution networks to improve grid operation (minimizing voltage deviation or grid losses).

This Deliverable builds on previous work by testing the models, control strategies, and optimization presented in D4.1 through HIL testing. In particular, the following tests have been carried out:

- MPC Controller Hardware-in-the-Loop (CHIL): The control strategy developed for the MPCs Triple Active Bridge has been implemented in the TI TMS320F28379D microcontroller board connected to the Typhoon HIL606 device. The last emulates the triple active bridge response using a switching model.
- MPC-based SOP Controller Hardware-in-the-Loop (CHIL): The control strategy devel-

oped for a three-port SOP based on the Triple Active Bridge has been implemented in the TI TMS320F28379D microcontroller board connected to the Typhoon HIL606 device. The last emulates the SOP response using an average model due to the limited digital PWM outputs of the microcontroller board. CHIL tests were carried out on a remote testbed provided by Typhoon HIL.

- SOP Power Hardware-in-the-Loop (PHIL): The PHIL test was conducted in IREC’s EnergyLab to validate the optimal operation of the MPC-based SOP defined in Deliverable D4.1. The test consisted of translating the MPC-based SOP into physical flexible devices that could adjust their absorbed or generated active and reactive power setpoints, just like the ports of an MPC-based SOP connected to the feeders of a distribution grid would do. PHIL tests were carried out at IREC’s Smart Lab facilities.

2.1 Real-time digital simulation and hardware in the loop

Before proceeding to the experimental validation, a brief explanation of the real-time digital simulations and hardware-in-the-loop concepts is presented. A clear understanding of these would help the reader to grasp the content of the rest of the deliverable.

2.1.1 Real-time digital simulation

Real-time digital simulations are performed in discrete time steps with constant step duration. The functions and equations representing the system are solved progressively, as functions of the variables’ values at the end of the preceding time step. The time required to solve these equations can be shorter or longer than the duration of the time step, as shown in Fig. 1, from [1]. These are typical cases of offline simulation, which is helpful in initial exploration of the models and controller design, providing more flexibility and a less constrained development environment in terms of plant size, level of detail in the models, controller complexity and assumptions, and computational burden. Conversely, in the real-time simulation, the simulator must return the outputs within the same time interval as its physical counterpart. In order to achieve real-time simulation, computations must be fast enough to end within the time interval. Once computations are completed, the simulator must remain idle until the next time step. If operations are not completed fast enough, real-time simulation is considered erroneous, which is known as an overrun. This represents a significant challenge from the perspective of the real-time simulators providers. Nevertheless, the value of these simulations for the users is significant. Assuming that the model’s level of detail is representative of the phenomena under study, the simulation outputs can represent the situations faced by control hardware in real-life conditions, which would validate both the selected control hardware and algorithms in scenarios close to real

Figure 1: Offline vs real-time simulation [1].

plant implementation.

A real-time simulation is deemed successful if it is executed without overruns. The choice of the real-time simulator depends on different criteria, including:

- Frequency of the highest transient to be simulated, defining the time step.
- Complexity and size of the system to simulate, defining the computing power.
- Number of I/O ports, depending on the number of connections with external physical devices.

Real-time digital simulation executes real system models synchronously connected to physical equipment, which is crucial for hardware-in-the-loop implementations.

2.1.2 Hardware in the loop simulation

Real-time simulation is mandatory when real physical devices are involved. However, the hardware included in the simulation loop varies depending on the objective of the test.

Controller hardware-in-the-loop is used to test a theoretical control strategy implemented in a real commercial controller board with relatively low computational power (compared to a HIL device) without having a plant prototype or commercial equipment, but a model of it is simulated in real time in a HIL device. This test allows assessing the controller's real response under less ideal conditions (measurement noise, digital signal processing, and analog-to-digital conversion delays, etc.). Furthermore, the power hardware-in-the-loop is used to test the response of a real equipment prototype under more ideal controller response executed in a HIL device with higher computational power and fewer input/output limitations than a commercial microcontroller. Furthermore, PHIL is used to evaluate the impact of real equipment or controllers in a wider system emulated in a HIL device.

In power systems and power electronics, HIL is gaining relevance and importance in industry and research applications [6]. In [7], the authors remarked on the relevance of power HIL simulations in electrical systems, presenting the real-time simulators' architectures and solvers, and other practical details, guiding the reader through the selection of different power amplification, interfacing algorithms, and their implications on complexity and stability of the simulations. Furthermore, in [8], the stability issues related to the power interface methods are analyzed in detail, and three methods for enhancing stability and accuracy in integrated power electronics and power systems PHIL simulations are evaluated experimentally. In power systems, DER integration, stability analysis, frequency and voltage regulation, cyber security, and protection validation are examples of applications where HIL has increased the fidelity of studies at lower costs. Furthermore, in power electronics, control strategies and converter prototype validation tests are the main applications of HIL. Moreover, stability studies validation for grid-connected converters under different grid conditions, control strategies, and converter topologies is also popular in the HIL literature [9]. In particular, authors in [10] used controller HIL to validate a new coordinated voltage control strategy based on distributed generators in distribution systems. The controller was run on a computer connected to an OPAL-RT HIL device through a DNP3 protocol server to send the setpoints to available distributed generators. Finally, novel approaches to further exploit the potential of HIL simulation have been proposed. Authors in [11] presented Multi-Hardware-in-the-Loop testing, which involves several real-time simulators that operate in parallel to achieve HIL validation of large-scale systems like power systems with several distributed energy resources. Furthermore, in [12], authors have proposed a novel slower-than-real-time simulation for controller HIL validation in very high switching frequency power converters. The proposed method has been tested in a buck converter switching at 200 kHz, proving the feasibility and accuracy of the approach.

3 Multiport converter digital real-time simulation

When validating models and controllers using hardware-in-the-loop methodology, the first stage of the process is to validate the capability of the HIL device to support digital real-time simulation (DRTS) of the model of interest. The smallest dynamic of the model should be well represented, avoiding overrun. Furthermore, this stage is useful to test the real-time implementation of the controller, achieving a first validation of the control strategy defined.

Once the multiport converter model simulation is validated in real-time, the CHIL procedure is used to validate the control strategy proposed. The later is presented in Section 4. This procedure is adopted to test the triple active bridge multiport converter.

3.1 Triple active bridge converter real-time simulation

Digital real-time simulation is used to validate the control methodologies proposed for the isolated multiport converter known as the triple active bridge (TAB). This topology operation and model were substantially reviewed in deliverables D2.1 of the project iPLUG. Therefore, the operation and model of the converter will be summarized in this deliverable.

3.1.1 Operation principle and power flow equations

The TAB is an extended topology derived from the dual active bridge (DAB) converter [13] but with three ports coupled by a three-winding high-frequency transformer as shown in Figure 2. Each transformer winding is represented by a reactance representing the leakage and added inductance, and it is connected to a full-bridge (FB) inverter and a filter capacitor C_p . All together forms a port p ($p = 1, 2, 3$). In this work, phase shift modulation is considered. Moreover, the single phase shift strategy is used, which considers that each FB inverter operates at a fixed frequency and at the same duty cycle of 50% to generate a square wave voltage v_p' . The generated voltages are shifted from each other by a controlled phase shift angle ϕ_{ij} ($i = 1, 2, j = 2, 3$ and $i \neq j$), thus allowing a controlled power flow [14].

To describe the operation and modeling of the TAB converter, without loss of generality, the port 1 is chosen as a reference, considering a phase shift ϕ_1 as 0. Furthermore, the magnetic inductance of the transformer L_m is assumed to be much greater than the leakage inductance L_i and therefore can be ignored. The different power flow directions in the TAB are presented in the Y-type and Δ -type primary-referred equivalent circuits of the TAB converter, see Figure 3. These equivalent circuits are also useful to derive the mathematical model of the converter.

Assuming that the losses are neglected, as in the case of DAB converter [13], the power transfer between two arbitrary ports can be defined as shown in (1) to (4).

Figure 2: Triple Active Bridge DC-DC converter.

Figure 3: (a) Y-type primary-referred equivalent circuit. (b) Δ -type primary-referred equivalent circuit.

$$P_{ij} = \frac{n_{ij}v_{dc_i}v_{dc_j}}{\omega_s L_{ij}} \phi_{ij} \left(1 - \frac{|\phi_{ij}|}{\pi}\right) \quad (1)$$

$$L_{ij} = L'_i + L'_j + \frac{L'_i L'_j}{L'_k}, \quad k = 1, 2, 3 \quad \text{and} \quad k \neq i, j \quad (2)$$

where v_{dc_i} and v_{dc_j} are the voltages on the port i and port j respectively, ω_s is the switching angular frequency, $\phi_{ij} = \phi_j - \phi_i$ is the phase shift between port i and port j , $n_{ij} = \frac{n_j}{n_i}$ is the turn ratio of the j -th port with respect to the i -th port, L_{ij} the equivalent

leakage inductance between port i and j defined by (2), and $L'_i = \frac{L_i}{n_{ij}^2} \forall i \in \{1, 2, 3\}$.

From equation 1, one can see that the transferable power depends on ϕ_{ij} , L_{ij} , ω_s and the port voltage levels. Therefore, the power flow can be controlled by varying ϕ_{ij} . Moreover, from Figure 3-(b), the total power at each port is defined as in (3), and the power flowing between each pair of ports can be derived from 1. Furthermore, to guarantee energy conservation, the power generated by port 1 should be equal to the sum of the powers absorbed by ports 2 and 3. In other words, the total power should be equal a zero, as depicted in (??).

$$P_1 = P_{12} + P_{13}$$

$$P_2 = P_{21} + P_{23} \quad (3)$$

$$P_3 = P_{31} + P_{32}$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^3 P_i = 0 \quad (4)$$

3.1.2 Full-Order Switched Model DRTS

During one switching period, the TAB converter toggles between six linear configurations, see Figure 2. By considering the transformer inductance currents (i_{L1}, i_{L2}, i_{L3}) and the output capacitor voltages (v_{dc2}, v_{dc3}) as state variables, the full-order switched model of the TAB converter can be obtained by applying Kirchhoff's laws over the equivalent circuits presented in Figure 3. The resulting set of equations is shown in (5) and (6).

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{di_{L1}}{dt} &= \left(\frac{1}{L_{12}} + \frac{1}{L_{13}} \right) u_1 v_{dc1} - \frac{n_{12}}{L_{12}} u_2 v_{dc2} - \frac{n_{13}}{L_{13}} u_3 v_{dc3} \\ \frac{di_{L2}}{dt} &= -\frac{1}{L_{12}} u_1 v_{in} + n_{12} \left(\frac{1}{L_{12}} + \frac{1}{L_{23}} \right) u_2 v_{dc2} - \frac{n_{13}}{L_{23}} u_3 v_{dc3} \\ \frac{di_{L3}}{dt} &= -\frac{1}{L_{13}} u_1 v_{in} - \frac{n_{12}}{L_{23}} u_2 v_{dc2} + n_{13} \left(\frac{1}{L_{13}} + \frac{1}{L_{23}} \right) u_3 v_{dc3} \\ \frac{dv_{dc2}}{dt} &= \frac{I_{dc2}}{C_2} - \frac{u_2 i_{L2}}{C_2} \\ \frac{dv_{dc3}}{dt} &= \frac{I_{dc3}}{C_3 R_3} - \frac{u_3 i_{L3}}{C_3} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

$$u_1 = \begin{cases} 1 & 0 < t \leq \frac{T}{2} \text{ (} S_{11}, S_{14} \text{ ON)} \\ -1 & \frac{T}{2} < t \leq T \text{ (} S_{12}, S_{13} \text{ ON)} \end{cases} \quad u_2 = \begin{cases} -1 & 0 < t \leq t_{\phi_2} \text{ (} S_{22}, S_{23} \text{ ON)} \\ 1 & t_{\phi_2} < t \leq \frac{T}{2} + t_{\phi_2} \text{ (} S_{21}, S_{24} \text{ ON)}, \\ -1 & \frac{T}{2} + t_{\phi_2} < t \leq T \text{ (} S_{22}, S_{23} \text{ ON)} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

$$u_3 = \begin{cases} -1 & 0 < t \leq t_{\phi_3} \text{ (} S_{32}, S_{33} \text{ ON)} \\ 1 & t_{\phi_3} < t \leq \frac{T}{2} + t_{\phi_3} \text{ (} S_{31}, S_{34} \text{ ON)} \\ -1 & \frac{T}{2} + t_{\phi_3} < t \leq T \text{ (} S_{22}, S_{23} \text{ ON)} \end{cases}$$

Figure 4: Open loop operation: (a) Phase shift (b) powers,

During the development of the TAB model in Typhoon HIL, several challenges are worth mentioning in this report. For instance, the use of gate-driving-signal (GDS) oversampling is essential in power electronics real-time simulations because it allows sampling the digital inputs driving the switching devices at a much higher rate than the main simulation time step, which improves the accuracy of the converter’s model response. In the case of the TAB, it was better to use switch-level GDS instead of global GDS. While global GDS oversampling samples all switches uniformly, switch-level GDS oversampling allows a more precise duty cycle computation for each individual switch within a simulation step. This is a critical distinction, since it allows a better alignment and coordination of switching events in the three H-bridges, improving the precision of the phase-shifted waveforms. The last is a very sensitive aspect in the power flow calculation at the TAB.

Another important aspect to consider is the core coupling in Typhoon HIL. Core coupling tools are used to split the complexity of a single circuit into sub-circuits so they can be processed in separate cores of the HIL device. In this case, the selection was tricky since the dynamics of the TAB are rather fast, and core couplings should be placed in sections of the model with slower dynamics. After a trial and error, and some internal analysis from Typhoon HIL, they suggested using TLM Core Couplings, which seemed to avoid topological conflicts and performed better than other coupling options.

To validate the simulation of the switching model in real-time, the open-loop simulations are performed. Furthermore, these simulations serve to illustrate the power flow coupling in the TAB.

In the open-loop simulation, the control variables ϕ_{12} and ϕ_{13} are varied independently. As can be seen from Figure 4, five possible scenarios have been performed:

- When $\phi_{12} = \phi_{13} > 0$ and $\phi_{23} = 0$, port 1 provides power to port 2 and port 3, and there is no power transfer between port 2 and port 3.
- when $\phi_{13} > \phi_{12} > 0$ and $\phi_{23} > 0$, port 1 provides power to port 2 and port 3, and port 3 receives power from port 2.
- When $\phi_{12} > \phi_{13} > 0$ and $\phi_{23} < 0$, port 1 provides power to port 2 and port 3, and port 3 provides power to port 2.
- When $\phi_{12} = \phi_{13} < 0$ and $\phi_{23} = 0$, port 1 receives power from port 2 and port 3, and there is no power transfer between port 2 and port 3.
- When $\phi_{12} < \phi_{13} < 0$ and $\phi_{23} > 0$, port 1 receives power from port 2 and port 3, and port 2 delivers power to port 3.
- When $\phi_{13} < \phi_{12} < 0$ and $\phi_{23} < 0$, port 1 receives power from port 2 and port 3, and port 2 receives power from port 3.

It is observed that although the phase shift at port i remains constant, its current I_i varies as the phase shift at port j changes. This phenomenon arises due to inductive coupling between the ports when no decoupling strategy is applied [15].

4 Multiport converter CHIL validation

Once the real-time simulation of the TAB converter model is done, the control strategy validation is performed and presented in this section. Before diving into the details of the MPC controller validation, a wider description of the CHIL and the testbed used in this work is presented as follows.

Controller Hardware-in-the-Loop is a testing technique used to validate control algorithms running on physical controllers by interfacing them with a real-time emulated plant model. In this setup, the controller interacts dynamically with the simulated system, responding to virtual plant conditions just as it would in a real-world scenario. By leveraging CHIL, it can accelerate controller development and validation while minimizing risks and costs, particularly when testing on the actual system is expensive or hazardous. Figure 5 shows a typical CHIL setup. The HIL device replaces the physical plant with a real-time simulated model while keeping the real controller board unchanged. This seamless transition allows for rigorous testing without the need for a physical system.

Figure 5: Typical CHIL setup block [2].

Once both the plant model and the control implementation are realized, the CHIL testbed must be connected. CHIL testbed uses a Typhoon HIL device to emulate the plant in real time, while the Texas Instruments (TI) microcontroller will execute the control strategy. The following section provides technical details of both and how the interaction between measurements and control actions is done.

4.1 HIL606

HIL606 system emulator is a hardware device that executes the model of the plant or controller (or both), depending on the HIL implemented. Furthermore, the HIL606 includes a set of inputs and outputs, and communication protocols that allow interaction with other equipment or controller boards, sensors, etc. This device is programmed using Typhoon HIL Control Center software, an interactive development tool that allows creating block

diagrams or script-based models and controllers. The integration of both the development tool and the emulation device allows for fast and transparent HIL test deployment. HIL606 main features include [16], [17]:

- ZU9EG Zynq UltraScale+ MPSoC processor with up to 8 processing core configurations.
- Simulation with sampling times of up to 0.2 μ s.
- 32 AIs and 64 AOs with 16-bit resolution and sampling rates of up to 5 MSPS and 1 MSPS for AOs and AIs, respectively.
- 64 DIs channels and 64 DOs channels with sampling rates of up to 280 MSPS and 3.5 ns oversampling on DIs.
- Paralleling capacity up to 16 components for joint simulation.
- Connectivity for real-time protocols: Ethernet, USB 3.0, RS-232, CAN, RS232, GPIO, HSSL.

4.2 Texas Instruments TMS320F28379D LaunchPad board

The Launchpad controller board implements the control strategy algorithm, receives measurements from the HIL device, and produces control actions that are sent back to the HIL device. The TMS320F28379D controller board, used in this work, is part of the C2000 family of 32-bit microcontrollers [18], which are specifically optimized for real-time control applications. These high-performance microcontrollers enhance closed-loop operation through advanced processing, sensing, and actuation capabilities, making them ideal for industrial motor drives, solar inverters, and precision signal processing. applications. Its main features include :

- C2000 32-bit real-time microcontrollers (MCUs) with 200-MHz.
- High-performance 32-bit CPU
- Up to 16 PWM outputs
- 12-bit ADC, 16 channels
- Up to 169 individually programmable, multiplexed GPIO pins with input filtering

4.3 Important setting parameters to take into account

- **Execution rate:** To ensure the HIL606 emulator accurately acquires signals with high fidelity, its data acquisition rate (“execution rate”) must be at least ten times faster than the fastest signal being processed. In this work, the fastest signals are PWM

waveforms with a frequency of 10 kHz, corresponding to an execution rate of 100 μs . Therefore, the emulator's execution rate must be at least 100 kHz, which corresponds to at most 10 μs .

- **Time step simulation:** The time step simulation must be equal to or smaller than the data sampling time. This ensures that the HIL606 device emulator processes all sampled signal points before advancing the simulation, preventing incomplete or skipped data. For this project, the value of the time step simulation is chosen as 1 μs .
- **Scaling signals:** The measurement analog signals applied to the HIL606 analog outputs and sampled by the controller must be scaled to the voltage range of the F28379D LaunchPad board (0-3V). To adjust the values, the signal configuration panel allows configuring the analog outputs that are sent to the TMS320F28379D LaunchPad board, applying a gain A and an offset to adjust the values to the range [0, 3]. The expression that allows this scaling to be carried out is the following:

$$Y_{[0,3]} = \frac{Y_{[\alpha,\beta]}}{A} + offset \quad \text{with} \quad A = \frac{\beta - \alpha}{3 - 0} \quad (7)$$

where

$$offset = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } \alpha = 0 \\ \frac{\beta}{A} & \text{if } \alpha < 0 \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

4.4 TAB power flow control validation

From (1), an expression for the current flowing at each port can be derived by dividing the power $P_{i,j}$ by the port voltage and summing the effect of each current $i_{i,j}$, resulting in (9). From (9), it can be seen that the power flow through the TAB converter ports is coupled to each other. This inherent power coupling represents a significant control challenge. To achieve a specific power distribution across the ports, the average currents in (9) must be controlled. Since the average current at each port depends on ϕ_{12} and ϕ_{13} , the TAB converter constitutes a coupled multiple-input, multiple-output (MIMO) system.

Decoupling the power flow in the TAB would simplify the control architecture while enhancing dynamic performance. To address this coupling issue, the proposed solution involves: (1) developing a linear small-signal model of the TAB converter, followed by (2) implementation of an inverse matrix decoupling strategy [15, 19–21].

$$\begin{aligned} i_2 &= -\frac{n_{12}v_{dc1}}{\omega_s L_{12}} \phi_{12} \left(1 - \frac{|\phi_{12}|}{\pi}\right) + \frac{n_{12}n_{13}v_{dc3}}{\omega_{sw} L_{23}} \phi_{23} \left(1 - \frac{|\phi_{23}|}{\pi}\right) \\ i_3 &= -\frac{n_{13}v_{dc1}}{\omega_s L_{13}} \phi_{13} \left(1 - \frac{|\phi_{13}|}{\pi}\right) - \frac{n_{12}n_{13}v_{dc2}}{\omega_{sw} L_{23}} \phi_{23} \left(1 - \frac{|\phi_{23}|}{\pi}\right) \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

The voltages v_{dc_i} at each port are assumed to be known and constant. Therefore, the

small signal model of the TAB converter can be derived by applying partial derivatives of i_2 and i_3 with respect to control variables ϕ_{12} and ϕ_{13} . The relationship between current variations and control variable variations can be defined as:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \Delta i_1 \\ \Delta i_2 \end{pmatrix} = G \begin{pmatrix} \Delta \phi_{12} \\ \Delta \phi_{13} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} g_{11} & G_{12} \\ G_{21} & G_{22} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \Delta \phi_{12} \\ \Delta \phi_{13} \end{pmatrix} \quad (10)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} G_{11} &= -\frac{V_{dc1}}{\omega_s L_{12}} \left(1 - 2 \frac{|\Phi_{12}|}{\pi}\right) - \frac{V_{dc3}}{\omega_s L_{23}} \left(1 - 2 \frac{|\Phi_{13} - \Phi_{12}|}{\pi}\right), \\ G_{12} &= \frac{V_{dc3}}{\omega_s L_{23}} \left(1 - 2 \frac{|\Phi_{13} - \Phi_{12}|}{\pi}\right), \\ G_{21} &= \frac{V_{dc2}}{\omega_s L_{23}} \left(1 - 2 \frac{|\Phi_{13} - \Phi_{12}|}{\pi}\right), \\ G_{22} &= -\frac{V_{dc1}}{\omega_s L_{13}} \left(1 - 2 \frac{|\Phi_{13}|}{\pi}\right) - \frac{V_{dc2}}{\omega_s L_{23}} \left(1 - 2 \frac{|\Phi_{13} - \Phi_{12}|}{\pi}\right) \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where Φ_{ij} is the steady state phase shift.

After the small signal model has been developed, the next step is to apply the inverse matrix decoupling strategy. This strategy aims to transform the coupled MIMO system into a set of independent SISO systems, where each output is influenced only by its corresponding input (Figure 6). It simplifies controller design by allowing a controller to be designed for each subsystem independently of the others. The approach involves applying the inverse of the gain matrix G (11) to the system, transforming it into a diagonal matrix H (12) with zero cross-coupling ($HG = I$, where $H = G^{-1}$ is the decoupling matrix and I is the identity matrix).

Figure 6: Block diagram of TAB converter and the decoupling network.

$$H = \begin{bmatrix} H_{11} & H_{12} \\ H_{21} & H_{22} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{G_{22}}{G_{11} * G_{22} - G_{12} * G_{21}} & -\frac{G_{12}}{G_{11} * G_{22} - G_{12} * G_{21}} \\ -\frac{G_{21}}{G_{11} * G_{22} - G_{12} * G_{21}} & \frac{G_{11}}{G_{11} * G_{22} - G_{12} * G_{21}} \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{with } (G_{11} * G_{22} - G_{12} * G_{21} \neq 0) \quad (12)$$

Figure 7 illustrates the CHIL test setup for the TAB converter. The TAB converter is mod-

Figure 7: CHIL test setup for the TAB converter.

eled in Typhoon HIL606 simulator device and, once compiled without errors, is loaded into the HIL SCADA for real-time simulation monitoring. Initially, the controller is implemented and tested in Typhoon HIL606. Once this step is successfully achieved, rapid controller prototyping is performed using the TI C2000 package provided by Typhoon HIL. The TI C2000 package automatically generates C-code based on the control tested in the simulator device and flashes it onto the microcontroller. This workflow, entirely performed within the Typhoon HIL environment, eliminates the need for external coding tools, facilitating controller testing, reducing human errors, and debugging time. The controller was embedded in a TI TMS320F28379D Launchpad board, which receives the voltage and current measurements from the HIL simulator device, executes the control logic, and generates twelve PWM signals to drive the three single-phase inverters of the TAB. These driving signals are sent back to the HIL simulator device, which simulates the system response and closes the loop, returning the measurements to the controller.

The dynamic performance of the TAB converter is evaluated in closed-loop operation using the circuit and control parameters listed in Table 1, and the results are discussed in the next subsection.

Table 1: TAB Converter and control parameters

Parameter	Value
Rated power: P_1, P_2, P_3	40, 20, 20 kW
Turn ratio: n_{12}, n_{13}	1, 1
Port voltage: $V_{dc1}, V_{dc2}, V_{dc3}$	450, 450, 450 V
Port inductance: L_1, L_2, L_3	10.743, 10.743, 10.743 μH
Port capacitance: C_1, C_2, C_3	2500, 2500, 2500 μF
Switching frequency: f_s	10 kHz
PI coefficients: $k_{p1} = k_{p2}, k_{i1} = k_{i2}$	10, 10^3

4.4.1 Closed loop operation

The following results present the performance of the TAB under the power flow control strategy validated through CHIL. The power flow control across the ports is achieved by a current controller, which regulates the secondary and tertiary port currents (I_2 and I_3). Using the decoupling matrix described in 4.4, two independent PI controllers—one for each port—were designed to mitigate cross-coupling effects. To evaluate the power flow control of the TAB converter, six changes in the operation point were performed. During the initial operating, Port 1 supplies 30 kW to Port 2, while Port 3 is not consuming or producing power. At $t = 0.03$ s, P_3^* changes, and Port 3 starts to consume 10 kW, which increases P_1 to 40 kW. At $t = 0.06$ s, Port 2 consumption increases to 45 kW, and at $t = 0.09$ s, Port 3 changes its operation from consumption to production, which reduces Port 1's power supply from 55 kW to 35 kW. Finally, additional changes are made in Ports 2 and 3, ending up with Port 1 supplying 30 kW, distributed equally among Ports 2 and 3, 15 kW each. The test results are depicted in Figure 8.

The dynamic response of the port currents demonstrates effective performance, with the controller exhibiting both rapid response and robustness against variations in port currents. Furthermore, the results clearly show the TAB converter's capability to achieve bidirectional power flow control.

4.5 Multiport soft open point control validation

This subsection briefly describes a TAB-based SOP multiport converter and its operation considerations. Later, the CHIL validation results are presented. For further details on the operation and control of the multiport SOP, the reader can refer to Deliverables D4.1, where these concepts were detailed.

Figure 8: TAB CHIL closed loop operation: (a) Currents (b) powers

4.5.1 TAB-based SOP operation and control

The SOP is a power electronics concept that aims to enhance normally open points or hard switches' operation in distribution networks. The most basic SOP topology is based on a 2-level Back-to-Back converter, which interconnects two different feeders [3]. Furthermore, since SOP is based on power electronics, its control capabilities unlock grid services provision similar to other power electronics-based solutions, increasing distribution networks' controllability, flexibility, and reliability. The triple active bridge can enhance SOP safety, voltage adaptation, and integration and sharing of distributed energy resources among multiple feeders of the AC distribution network [22].

Figure 9 shows the TAB-based SOP. In this Deliverable, the grids connected to each AC port are represented by Thevenin equivalents at the point of common coupling. Furthermore, the DC port is connected to a DC energy resource represented by a controlled current source.

On the other hand, Figure 10 presents the block diagrams of the control strategy adopted for the inverters in the SOP. The inverters are controlled using a grid-following strategy realized in the dq synchronous reference frame, and VdcQ and PQ control modes are for inverters 1 and 2, respectively. Since the inverter's control is developed in the synchronous

Figure 9: TAB-based SOP multiport converter

Figure 10: TAB-based SOP control diagrams: a) Inverters control (VdcQ and PQ control modes), b) PLL block diagram

reference frame, a PLL is used as a synchronization method. Figure 10b presents the block diagram for the PLL controller.

4.5.2 TAB-based SOP CHIL results

This section presents the CHIL simulation results of a TAB-based soft-open point. Figure 11 shows the setups used for the TAB-based SOP CHIL validation tests. The control algorithms for inverter 1 and the TAB are embedded in the microcontroller. On the other hand, the inverter 2 controller and the plant model (grid and TAB-based SOP) are simulated in real time by the Typhoon HIL device.

Considering the operation described in Section 4.5.1 and the parameters presented in Table 2, the results of the CHIL are presented in Figure 12. For the validation of the controller, power disturbances are applied at ports 2 and 3 as follows:

- t=0.2s, port 2 active power increases from 0 to 20kW.

Figure 11: CHIL setup for the TAB-based SOP control validation.

Table 2: TAB-Based SOP parameters

Parameter	Value
AC voltage RMS: v_{ac1}, v_{ac2}	230, 230 V
AC grid frequency: f_{ac1}, f_{ac2}	50, 50 Hz
AC grid impedance: $R_{grid1,2}, X_{grid1,2}$	0.3, 0.1 Ohm
Inverter rated power: S_{inv1}, S_{inv2}	50, 50 kVA
Inverter inductor filter: L_{inv1}, L_{inv2}	1.2, 1.2 mH
Inverter resistor filter: R_{inv1}, R_{inv2}	0.1, 0.1 Ohm
Port DC voltage: $v_{dc1}, v_{dc2}, v_{dc3}$	780, 780, 400 V
Port TAB inductance: L_1, L_2, L_3	34.5, 69.9, 69.9 μ H
Port capacitance: C_1, C_2, C_3	3.4, 1.7 mF
Switching frequency: $f_{sw-tab}, f_{inv1,2}$	20, 10 kHz
TAB port 1 gains: K_{p1}, K_{i1}	$0.25e^{-3}, 3.7e^{-3}$
TAB port 2 gains: K_{p2}, K_{i2}	$0.52e^{-3}, 7.8e^{-3}$
inv_1 current control gains: $K_p^{i_{inv1}}, K_i^{i_{inv1}}$	9, 1900
inv_1 v_{dc} control gains: $K_p^{v_{dc_{inv1}}}, K_i^{v_{dc_{inv1}}}$	1, 372
inv_1 Q control gains: $K_p^{Q_{inv1}}, K_i^{Q_{inv1}}$	$20e^{-6}, 0.12$
inv_2 current control gains: $K_p^{i_{inv2}}, K_i^{i_{inv2}}$	5, 970
inv_2 P & Q control gains: $K_p^{P_{inv2}}, K_i^{P_{inv2}}$	$20e^{-6}, 0.06$
$inv_{1,2}$ PLL control gains: $K_p^{PLL_{inv1,2}}, K_i^{PLL_{inv1,2}}$	0.1, 1

- $t=0.4s$, port 2 active power increases from 20kW to 40kW.
- $t=0.6s$, port 3 active power increases from 0 to 20kW.
- $t=0.8s$, port 3 active power increases from 20kW to 30kW.
- $t=1s$, port 3 load is partially and suddenly lost (final active power is 6kW).
- $t=1.2s$, port 3 load is recovered and reaches 30kW again.

Figure 12 shows the behavior of the TAB-based SOP under several changes in the operating point. Figure 12a shows that voltages at each port are regulated successfully. The port 1 voltage regulation is faster than ports 2 and 3, which improves the DC voltage response at ports 2 and 3. When $t \sim 1s$, the AC current at port 1 reaches its nominal values (see Figure 12d), and at $t = 1s$, the port 3 load is partially lost, decreasing by 26 kW (see Figure 12b). Figure 12a shows a large voltage peak in v_{dc3} , while ports 1 and 2 are less affected by this change. After reaching steady state, the load at port 3 is recovered at $t = 1.2s$, creating a big voltage dip in v_{dc3} , following an overshoot and reaching steady state

Figure 12: TAB-based SOP CHIL results: a) DC voltage response at ports 1, 2, and 3, b) Active power response at ports 1, 2, and 3, c) AC grid 1 current response, d) AC grid 1 current response (Zoom)

after 0.2s. This overshoot is also observed in the active power and AC current at port 1, which is supplying the power demanded by ports 2 and 3. Moreover, the voltages at Ports 1 and 2 remain stable and are less affected by this disturbance. It is clear that the dynamic remains as expected, even when the SOP is subject to faults in one of its ports, like the loss of port 3 simulated between $t=1s$ and $t=1.2s$. Finally, it is important to note that port 3 is more susceptible to power disturbances in other ports because its lower nominal voltage leads to larger current excursions under unwanted power flows linked to port coupling.

5 Power Hardware in the Loop

This Power Hardware-in-the-Loop (PHIL) test is designed to integrate a physical layer into the Optimal Power Flow (OPF) formulation for optimal dispatch of active and reactive power setpoints in a multi-port soft open point. Specifically, the test is carried out considering a tri-port soft open point connected to two feeders of the IEEE 33 bus system, as outlined in Deliverable D4.1 and shown in Figure 13.

This test aims to evaluate the feasibility and performance of sending power setpoints resulting from the OPF to load cabinets connected to grid emulators. The grid emulators are expected to represent the behaviour of specific buses of the IEEE 33 bus system, specifically buses 18 and 33, where the SOP is supposed to be connected. This testbed also allows evaluating the transient behavior of the system when power setpoints are sent, in a more realistic setting thanks to the addition of the physical equipment.

Specifically, the main objectives are the following:

- Validation: Ensure that the active and reactive power setpoints calculated by OPF with the SOP can be acquired by the physical devices.
- Verification: Observe and analyse the system's transient behaviour in response to real-time changes of the power setpoints in the emulated SOP.
- Characterization: Quantify the operational benefits of employing the multiport SOP in terms of voltage regulation and loss minimization of the simulated distribution grid.

Figure 13: Tri-port SOP connected to two feeders of the IEEE 33 bus system.

5.1 Test description

In a PHIL setup, physical power hardware, such as generators, motors, transformers, and power electronic devices, are interconnected with a simulation environment, typically implemented in software. This simulation environment replicates the behavior of the entire power system, including generation, transmission, and distribution networks. The hardware components interact with the simulated environment in real-time, enabling the

Figure 14: PHIL architecture

Figure 15: EnergySmartLab SCADA

analysis of the performance of the hardware under various operating conditions, including normal operation, fault conditions, and transient events. An example of the hardware and software involved in a PHIL testbed is shown in Figure 14.

5.1.1 Testbed components: Software

The software employed for the PHIL tests includes Opal RT-Lab, Matlab-Simulink and the microgrid SCADA available in the Energy SmartLab. RT-lab includes a Simulink model of the IEEE 33 bus system with the tri-port SOP.

The SCADA system, in Figure 15 enables monitoring each device in the PHIL testbed. Specifically, the red arrows connecting the switches and the cabinets represent an active connection between the OPAL-RT and the cabinets. On the other hand, the cabinet windows describe the working conditions of the cabinets, including the active and reactive power setpoints.

Figure 16: IREC's Opal-RT platform

5.1.2 Testbed components: Hardware

For the physical equipment section within the laboratory environment, a 15kV network emulator from Cinergia and its proprietary HMI and Dashboard software are employed. Additionally, the three-phase busbar of the Smartlab microgrid, the Smartlab microgrid's proprietary SCADA system, and a 4kW network/load emulator cabinet controlled via Raspberry Pis executing Python scripts for TCP/IP, CAN, ModbusTCP communications, control, and monitoring is utilized.

Opal-RT Opal-RT, shown in Figure 16, is a real-time simulation platform for the design, testing and validation of power systems, power electronics and controls. They are widely used for HIL, CHIL and PHIL testing, since they allow the integration of physical components into simulated environment. In this context, they allow the real-time execution of the IEEE 33 bus system and the flexibility to integrate the optimization algorithm developed for the multiport SOP operation.

Cinergia grid emulator The grid emulator, Figure 17, acts as the power source for the cabinets. Its role is to recreate the power values that are simulated in the Simulink model and provide them to real-world electric loads, the cabinets. It receives as input the RMS voltage from the grid bus selected as the physical bus operated in the laboratory, and provides the active and reactive power requested by the cabinets. Hence, it receives communication signals through Modbus from the computer and provides as output actual electric power to the cabinets. The grid emulator comes with a monitoring dashboard, that allows checking the status of the system in terms of voltages, currents and power, and define setpoints and characteristics of the waveforms, such as harmonics, frequency etc.

Load emulator cabinets The load cabinet, Figure 18 on the left, acts as the physical loads corresponding to one bus of the system. In this test, bus 18 has been chosen as the one simulated both in the virtual and physical environment. Considering that the maximum acceptable power of the cabinets is 4 kW, the power in the simulated grid must be scaled accordingly. This cabinet receives the active power (P) and reactive power (Q) inputs from the computer hosting the optimizer through Modbus, and the physical electric power from

Figure 17: Cinergia grid emulator

Figure 18: Load emulator cabinets

the grid emulator. The cabinet supports different operating modes for controlling the power setpoints: active power (P) only, active power with power factor ($P/\cos \phi$), and active and reactive power (P/Q). These modes are configured directly via the SCADA system interfaced with the cabinet. Since the optimizer sends P and Q signals to the cabinets, the P/Q mode must be selected to establish the communication correctly.

5.2 Test phases

The PHIL test was divided into several phases that progressively led to the final result.

Communication between centralized optimizer and power cabinets Figure 19 shows the setup of the initial test, whose main objective was to verify the Modbus connection between the computer running the optimal MPC-based SOP operation script and the physical

Figure 19: Modbus connection test between the optimal MPC-based SOP operation script and the physical cabinet.

Figure 20: Test design for power connection and current measurements verification.

cabinet connected to the grid emulator and representing one of the SOP’s ports. In this phase, the optimizer sent P and Q to the physical cabinets. The communication was established with a Modbus connection through the laboratory network, enabled by a dedicated VPN. The communication was easily achieved thanks to Matlab’s built-in `modbus` function. The values sent by the optimizer are written in specific register channels, corresponding to the control inputs of the cabinet.

Power connection and current measurements from Grid Emulator In this phase of the PHIL test, additional elements were integrated beyond the optimizer and the cabinet. These included the grid emulator, the OPAL-RT simulator and the computer hosting RT-Lab, the software environment for OPAL-RT.

Figure 20 illustrates the architecture of this test setup and its main components.

Opal-RT is employed to simulate the IEEE 33-bus distribution grid in real-time. It can connect to the grid emulator either through Modbus or low voltage analog signals, depending on the nature of the signals being exchanged. Modbus is used when only RMS values are communicated, whereas analog signals are required when instantaneous data is required.

In these tests, Modbus communication was employed, since the test did not involve high speed, primary control actions or transient evaluation. The goal of this phase was to evaluate the power exchange between the grid emulator and the load cabinet and verify the measurement feedback under steady-state RMS conditions. The active and reactive power setpoints, in this intermediate phase, were manually controlled through Modbus-Poll application and were not resulting from the optimizer.

The grid emulator and the load cabinet together physically represent the a single port of the MPC-based SOP, considered as connected to bus 18 of the IEEE 33 bus distribution grid.

The signals exchanged during the tests include on one hand the RMS voltage signals sent from OPAL-RT to the grid emulator. On the other, the RMS current signals measured by the grid emulator and sent back to the Opal-RT.

The grid emulator replicates the RMS voltage signals coming from the bus 18 of the grid modelled in Opal-RT. The signals are scaled from the medium voltage of the benchmark system (12.6 kV nominal), to a low voltage of 230 V nominal. Similarly, the current fed back to the model is scaled based on the combination of the voltage scaling factor and power ratio between the physical cabinets, with a low power capacity in the order of kW, and the power level in the simulation, in the order of MW.

The instantaneous current values, starting from the RMS measurements received from the the grid emulator, are reproduced through a set of three, balanced controlled current generators connected to bus 18, as in Figure 21.

Since the input signals are RMS values, the three-phase currents are synchronized to the rest of the grid is created by adding the phase angle measurement from a PLL and a power factor calculator depending on the P and Q setpoints in the cabinet, as shown in Figure 22

When using analog signals inputs to the model, the synchronization blocks are not needed, since the signal can be directly reproduced by the controlled current generators.

In the initial tests, random values of P and Q setpoints were manually sent to the cabinets in order to validate the setup. The active power setpoints were accurately tracked by the grid emulator. However, a mismatch occurred between the measured reactive power and the corresponding setpoint. The mismatch was not a constant offset or a linear dependence. For this reason, this issue was solved by testing multiple reactive power setpoint values

Figure 21: Current generators connected to bus 18.

Figure 22: Current waveform synchronization.

and adjusting the setpoint over the power capacity range of the cabinet.

Integration of MPC-based SOP optimizer with Opal-RT and physical equipment

The last preliminary test consisted in sending the setpoints directly from the optimizer to the cabinet, for one port, and to the model (connected to another bus) for the other port, as shown in Figure 23, instead of manually setting them through Modbus Poll.

Regarding the communication from the optimizer to the cabinet, fast changes in the cabinet setpoints resulted in the failure and the emergency switch off of the cabinets and required multiple manual resets to restart testing. This issue was probably caused by the presence of large transients following the setpoint change.

The solution was achieved by converting the one-step changes coming from optimizer in gradual setpoint changes with intermediate discrete changes in the setpoints. Nevertheless, while the presence of large and fast transients may not be an issue when considering steady-state operation and secondary controllers, the phenomenon should be better explored when implementing and testing local primary controls.

Figure 23: Integration of MPC-based SOP optimizer with Opal-RT and physical equipment

Regarding the other port of the MPC-based SOP, it is simulated through a dynamic load model driven by external active and reactive power setpoints. These setpoints, in principle, should come directly from the optimizer through Modbus communication. However, direct Modbus communication to Opal-RT appears to be blocked due to constraints related to cyber-security issues, since Opal directly controls the grid emulator voltage in the laboratory, and its remote control should be limited. For this reason, the setpoints in the other port are set by reporting the results of the optimizer manually to the model.

5.3 Final tests

The Figure 24 shows the behavior of voltage, current and active power during the simulation, as directly measured by the grid emulator and shown by its GUI. In the initial test, three main phases can be identified:

1. The grid emulator and the cabinet are connected but not driven by the simulated grid in Opal-RT: voltage, current and power are constant. In order to correctly start the test, grid emulators should be initially set to 230 V.
2. The simulation in Opal RT is started and the voltage measured at bus 18 of the simulated grid is transferred to the grid emulator. The voltage changes from 230 V to approximately 220 V, since the bus 18 is at the end of the feeder, after an initial brief transient when starting the simulation.
3. The optimization is run and the active power setpoint associated with voltage deviation minimization is sent to the cabinet. The figure shows the gradual change in active

Figure 24: Grid emulator GUI during the first test.

power and current. In this scenario, the active power setpoint is very low, whereas the reactive power is employed to compensate the voltage. Negative active power refers to power injection from the SOP’s port to the grid.

4. The reactive power setpoint is sent to the cabinet with step changes. The steps, larger than the ones for active power, are reflected by the larger variation of the current in this phase.

Phase 4 of Figure 24 illustrates how the voltage is restored to a value much closer to the 230 V nominal thanks to the voltage deviation minimization strategy.

An additional test was carried out, in which the SOP setpoint was changed first based on loss minimization and then voltage deviation minimization results.

The different phases are shown in Figure 25:

1. The test starts with the benchmark IEEE 33 bus system without the SOP. The system is in steady state and the physical equipment is connected but does not exchange energy.
2. The optimizer for grid loss minimization is executed and the scaled setpoint results are sent to the cabinet. The step change in the active power setpoint, in order to limit over/undervoltages, is shown in the Figure 25. The active power step changes are accompanied by large overvoltage transients and an increase in the current magnitude. The step change of reactive power, not shown in the figure, follows right after the active power setpoint is achieved. It can be noticed in the figure through the slight changes in voltage and current values. Once the setpoint is achieved, the simulation starts working in the new steady state.

Figure 25: Grid emulator GUI. 1) Opal-RT simulation start, 2) Loss minimization configuration of the SOP, 3) Voltage deviation minimization configuration of the SOP.

3. In the third phase, the working mode of the SOP is changed to voltage deviation minimization, by running again the optimizer and sending the new setpoints to the cabinet. Similar transients are shown in this phase. The current plot shows first a decrease in the magnitude due to the active power setpoint change, followed by an increase due to the reactive power change.

6 Conclusions

This report described the final research outcomes of Work Package 4, mainly focused on the validation of control and coordination of MPCs operating in distribution networks.

The Deliverable was divided into three main chapters.

In Chapter 3, the triple active bridge model developed in Typhoon HIL ecosystem is presented. The open-loop simulations demonstrated the capacity of the HIL device to run real-time simulations with such a complex topology. However, the development process showed that model partitioning was needed to run this switching model, increasing the computational burden of implementing the switching model of the complete soft-open point topology. Therefore, the soft-open point model used in Chapter 4 is an average model.

Next, in Chapter 4, the controller HIL simulations of a TAB and a TAB-based soft open point were presented. First, the TAB power flow decoupling control was validated in standalone operation using the switching model. The closed-loop simulation results were discussed under different operational conditions. At this stage, the control strategy of the TAB was embedded in a Texas Instruments microcontroller. The C2000 package tool available in Typhoon HIL ecosystem for rapid prototyping was used to create the controller C code

and flash it into the microcontroller, removing the coding stage and reducing the implementation and debugging time. Once the TAB controller was validated in standalone mode, the complete SOP model was introduced, and the TAB-based SOP controller was validated. The TAB-based SOP was tested under different operating conditions, including a fault that included a partial load loss in the DC port.

Finally, Chapter 5 described the validation of the centralized controller for the optimal coordination of multiple MPCs. The optimization strategy developed in T4.3 was coded in MATLAB and executed on a laptop with relatively low computational power. Furthermore, the IEEE 33 bus system was developed in Simulink and executed in the OPAL-RT real-time simulator. The testbed created for this validation enabled the communication between the Optimization laptop, the OPAL-RT, and a set of equipment in the laboratory that would exchange active and reactive power with a grid emulator that represented the point of common coupling of the MPC with the grid. The results of the tests validated the results obtained for voltage minimization in the IEEE 33 bus system.

In conclusion, the research outcomes presented in this deliverable, including the DRTS validation, CHIL, and PHIL simulations, validated the control strategies proposed in previous tasks under experimental scenarios. The use of real controllers and real power equipment has a big impact on the implementation of new control and optimization strategies, and in the case of MPCs, relying on a single controller could be challenging, considering the increased number of inputs and outputs when compared to conventional power converters.

References

- [1] J. Bélanger, P. Venne, J.-N. Paquin *et al.*, “The what, where and why of real-time simulation,” *Planet Rt*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 25–29, 2010.
- [2] I. Typhoon HIL. (2024) What-is controller hardware-in-the-loop (c-hil) simulation. [Online]. Available: <https://www.typhoon-hil.com/blog/what-is-controller-hardware-in-the-loop-c-hil-simulation/>
- [3] X. Jiang, Y. Zhou, W. Ming, P. Yang, and J. Wu, “An overview of soft open points in electricity distribution networks,” *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 1899–1910, 2022.
- [4] M. Deakin, I. Sarantakos, D. Greenwood, J. Bialek, P. C. Taylor, and S. Walker, “Comparative analysis of services from soft open points using cost–benefit analysis,” *Applied Energy*, vol. 333, p. 120618, 2023.
- [5] A. C. Henao-Muñoz *et al.*, “Report on system modelling, simulation and advanced controllers for enhanced functionalities and services provision from multiport converters,” Tech. Rep., 2024. [Online]. Available: https://iplug-he.eu/?page_id=284
- [6] C. S. Edrington, M. Steurer, J. Langston, T. El-Mezyani, and K. Schoder, “Role of power hardware in the loop in modeling and simulation for experimentation in power and energy systems,” *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol. 103, no. 12, pp. 2401–2409, 2015.
- [7] G. F. Lauss, M. O. Faruque, K. Schoder, C. Dufour, A. Viehweider, and J. Langston, “Characteristics and design of power hardware-in-the-loop simulations for electrical power systems,” *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 63, no. 1, pp. 406–417, 2016.
- [8] G. Lauss and K. Strunz, “Accurate and stable hardware-in-the-loop (hil) real-time simulation of integrated power electronics and power systems,” *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 36, no. 9, pp. 10920–10932, 2021.
- [9] M. R. Nasab, R. Cometa, S. Bruno, G. Giannoccaro, and M. I. Scala, “Power systems simulation and analysis: A review on current applications and future trends in drts of grid-connected technologies,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 12, pp. 121320–121345, 2024.
- [10] A. Newaz, J. Ospina, and M. O. Faruque, “Controller hardware-in-the-loop validation of coordinated voltage control scheme for distribution systems containing inverter-based distributed generation,” *IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Industrial Electronics*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 332–341, 2022.

- [11] S. D’Arco, S. Sanchez-Acevedo, and J. A. Suul, “Multi-hardware-in-the-loop laboratory testing of power converters and intelligent electronic devices for large-scale power system applications,” *IEEE Open Journal of Power Electronics*, vol. 5, pp. 1520–1533, 2024.
- [12] H. Bai, G. Huang, C. Liu, Y. Huangfu, and F. Gao, “A controller hil testing approach of high switching frequency power converter via slower-than-real-time simulation,” *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 71, no. 8, pp. 8690–8702, 2024.
- [13] R. W. De Doncker, D. M. Divan, and M. H. Kheraluwala, “A three-phase soft-switched high-power-density dc-dc converter for high-power applications,” *IEEE Trans. Ind. Appl.*, vol. 27, pp. 63–73, 1991.
- [14] J. He, Y. Chen, J. Lin, J. Chen, L. Cheng, and Y. Wang, “Review of modeling, modulation, and control strategies for the dual-active-bridge dc/dc converter,” *Energies*, vol. 16, no. 18, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/1996-1073/16/18/6646>
- [15] P. Koochi, A. J. Watson, J. C. Clare, T. B. Soeiro, and P. W. Wheeler, “A survey on multi-active bridge dc-dc converters: Power flow decoupling techniques, applications, and challenges,” *Energies*, vol. 16, no. 16, p. 5927, 2023.
- [16] I. Typhoon HIL. (2024) Hil606 hardware user guide. [Online]. Available: www.typhoon-hil.com/documentation/typhoon-hil-hardware-manual/hil606_user_guide/topics/hil606_abstract.html
- [17] ——. (2024) Hil606 brochure. [Online]. Available: www.typhoon-hil.com/wp-content/uploads/2024/12/Typhoon-HIL606-Brochure2024.12-Updated-tables.pdf
- [18] I. Texas Instruments. (2024) Tms320f2808 card data sheet. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ti.com/lit/ds/symlink/tms320f2808.pdf?ts=1752410097737>
- [19] C. Zhao, S. D. Round, and J. W. Kolar, “An isolated three-port bidirectional dc-dc converter with decoupled power flow management,” *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 23, no. 5, pp. 2443–2453, 2008.
- [20] N. Koya, Y. K., and W. Keiji, “Implementation of decoupling power flow control system in triple active bridge converter rated at 400v, 10kw, and 20khz,” *IEEJ Jour. Ind. Appl.*, vol. 7, no. 5, pp. 410–415, 2011.
- [21] D. Biswas, I. and Kastha and P. Bajpai, “Small signal modeling and decoupled controller design for a triple active bridge multiport dc-dc converter,” *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 36, no. 2, pp. 1856–1869, 2020.

- [22] S. Harrison, B. Soltoswski, A. Pepiciello, A. Camilo Henao, A. Y. Farag, M. Beza, L. Xu, A. Egea-Àlvarez, M. Cheah-Mañé, and O. Gomis-Bellmunt, "Review of multiport power converters for distribution network applications," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 203, p. 114742, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1364032124004684>

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